

Securing E-commerce Big Data Security In Cloud: An Exploration

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Abstract

Protecting digital information from unauthorized arrival, misconduct, or theft at any levels of its lifecycle is the concept of data security. Big data and cloud computing continue to face a number of challenges when they become more widely used in e-commerce. In the framework of cloud, computing, this article mainly discusses about security of big data based on e-commerce.

Many businesses need efficient methods to store and process enormous quantities of data. Scalable resources and considerable financial benefits in the form of reduced costs of operation are provided by cloud computing as an enabler. This paper is discuss on the essential problem of security of e-commerce in information and could computing storage. The focus of this research is to provide a secure environment for online transaction .We discuss some collection of methods to evaluate the security issues with large data scale to achieve this goal.

Keywords Cloud computing, Big Data, RSA, 3DES, Blowfish.

Introduction

E-commerce is an internet business practiced by various businesses to offer their commodities, products, and etc. They have more data to store for this. Some businesses have their own platforms for storing data, but it becomes quite challenging to do so when business volumes of data and information transmission increase. To store data, they therefore used an external platform.

There are currently an estimated 2.14 billion online shoppers worldwide, with 200 million prime members using the Amazon website.com. The first company offering cloud storage services is Amazon. As e-commerce spreads around the globe, companies may now offer software, clothing, house wares, or services for site design, and thus there will be a problem with data security in the cloud.

A large quantity of data is being generated and stored as a result a rapid expansion in the use of internet-based technologies, such as cloud computing. They are referred to as a Big Data because of the diversity, space and volume of the data. Several companies use the analysis of these large data to improve their business strategies and reap rewards. Additionally, the increased use of the internet led to the e-commerce, or electronic commerce, operations.

Rapid expansion of the use of internet based technology, such as digital technology, cloud computing, etc, is creating and saving huge quantities of data. Lots of companies analyze such huge amount of information to enhance their company goals and profit. Companies like Amazon, Google, and Microsoft offer platforms for storing your data in cloud. Data storage on the cloud is referred to as cloud computing.

Aim of study

Data on transactions or business activity evolves over time. These data are organized and gathered from a variety of sources, such as customer relationship programmers' (e.g., company-maintained profiles of clients, the occurrence of consumer complaints), and sales data. Data on transactions or business activity evolve as time passes as a consequence of interactions between the client as well as the company.

Review of Literature

E-Commerce is a large online business running in current era. Every business has different approaches to cloud security which become big challenges now a day. In cloud

computing using Saas, Pass, laas methods are used for doing or securing online business.

In this research paper we use RAS, DEA, and Blowish algorithm to secure the data in cloud environment based on previous article publishing such as (1)IJARSCT (2)IJRETS (3)WIKIPEDIA (4)Research gates.

Methodology

1.1 Cloud Computing

Cloud computing is a computer technology that uses internet network to provide 14 cloud storage services. Cloud computing services supplied by specific companies called cloud provider, which handle the resource allocation and eventually, even the complete management of the services. Cloud computing is invented by J.C.R Licklider in the 1960s work with ARPANET to connect data from everywhere at any time.

1.2 Services in cloud computing

Services offered by cloud computing include email, storage, backup, and data retrieval, application creation and testing, data analysis, audio and video streaming, and on-demand software delivery. Public services are those that are offered online for a fee, 18 whereas private services are housed in networks for specific clients. Large businesses that conduct e-commerce must pay a fee to store their data.

Three alternative methods can be used to install cloud services. Clouds are public, private, or hybrid here public cloud data accessible to everyone. All businesses that conduct online business use public cloud services to market their brands. Private cloud computing that only authorized users can access. Hybrid gives access to both 17 people with public and private access.

Analysis

Cloud Computing Services

i. Infrastructure is a type of cloud service that offers virtualized computer resources over the internet. Control over IT infrastructure, including server, storage, and networking resources, as well as businesses using virtual machines, is provided via the cloud. More readily available data allows businesses to work more quickly. IaaS offers its own setup and functionality for the infrastructure. The companies Linode, Hostwinds, Microsoft, and Digital Ocean offer IaaS services.

ii. The platform as a Service (PaaS) offers straightforward and practical offerings. It is adaptable to each use. Companies situated in America such as IBM, Sales force, Red Hat, and Elastic Beanstalk offer PaaS services.

iii. Software as Service (SAAS) application level services offered by SAAS companies includes business analysis, marketing automation, and customer relationship management. The provider will deliver service after allowing each subscriber client or cloud tenant access to run on host servers. SAS is provided by businesses like Adobe, SAP.

2. Big data used in the E-commerce

2.1 E-commerce

Large amounts of information are contained in big data. E-commerce refers to the purchasing and selling of goods and services online. A potential component of the definition of an e-commerce company is affiliate marketing tactics. You can utilize social media, a well-known store like Amazon, your own website, or other e-commerce channels to boost your online sales.

A compact disc was treated at the first-ever internet transaction on August 11, 1994. An important change in the way we shop and conduct business would result from this transaction. E-commerce is buying and selling of products and services online was created at that time. A vast network of digital platform and technology including website, builder, payment and social media sales channels, fuel e-commerce today. Global e-commerce sales will total \$8 billion and makes up 23.6% of all retail by 2026 is expected. New technologies are advanced, making easier for companies to market their goods online. There are different 16 types of E-commerce business platform.

Types of E- Commerce

i. Business-to-Consumer (B2C)

Here the company will sell their goods directly to the customer. The customer can browse their website and look at products, picture, read reviews. Then they place their order and the company ships the good directly to them like Amazone, Flipkard, and Jabong etc.

ii. **Bussiness -to-Bussiness (B2B)**

Here the companies are doing bussiness with each other. The main consumer is not involved. So the online transactions only involve the manufacturers, wholesalers, etc.

iii. **Consumer –to-consumer (C2C)** Where the consumers are in directly contact with each other. It helps people to sell their goods and assets directly to an interested party. OLX provide direct service to the customer.

2.2 Big Data

Big data is information that is more varied and is arriving at more rapidly and in greater numbers. Data is a term for larger, more complex information collections, particularly those from new data sources. Big Data ecommerce is a type of ecommerce that utilizes big data analytics services. It helps to improve customer experience, personalize the shopping experience, and increase profit.

Big Data is a big deal, if collected and utilized in the right manner, it can change the future of every business. 'Big Data' ecommerce platforms are frequently adaptable, scalable, and feature-rich. Without having to worry about data loss, it enables ecommerce enterprises to handle millions of daily visitors. In order to personalize the customer experience across all websites, devices, and channels, organizations can use big data ecommerce to give them insights into the shopping habits of their customers.

Large –scale big data and analytics are used in e-commerce, a type of enhance customer engagement, personalise the buying experience, and boost sales. Big data e-commerce engages clients primarily through two methods: individualised recommendation services and improved access to product details. According to International Data Corporation it is estimated that the digital universe of data will grow 61% to 175 zettabytes by 2025. There are different types of big data used in e-commerce i.e. Data on transactions or business activity, Clicking-stream data, Video data, voice data etc.

Types of Big Data

1. **Data on transaction or business activity:**

Data on transactions or business activity evolves over time. These data are organized and gathered from a variety of sources, such as customer relationship programmers' (e.g., company-maintained profiles of clients, the occurrence of consumer complaints), and sales data. Data on transactions or business activity evolve as time passes as a sequence of interactions between the client as well as the company.

2. **Click-stream data:**

In current networked world, internet and social media marketing, like the consumption of click-stream data, are essential to a business's continuing promotional plan since they allow management to make smart tactical and strategic choices. Click stream data is gathered from online advertisements and websites that sell goods as well as posts to social media including tweets that websites, and Instagram wall comments.

3. **Video data**

Online retailers are ready to use video information in addition to click stream information or transaction data when utilized alongside image analysis technological advances. The term "video data" refers to information acquired by collecting live views. E-commerce companies possess the ability to evaluate extremely unstructured data, which can include video and audio, and this material can be useful for companies that sell online.

4. **Voice data**

Voice data, or details obtained by means of phone conversations, call centres, or

customer service, is another category of data belonging to the big data family. Voice data may be utilized to assess consumer purchase patterns and draw in new customers. After looking at all four distinct user behaviour types of click, gather, add into cart, and buy.

Because customers view things by browsing on them but do not always add them to a list or cart, the researcher found that clicks had the highest proportion. Clients were categorized into four categories in addition to the Frequency, and Material (RFM) model: VIP, which is loyal, important customer, and those inclined to leave the business. These technologies help online retailers connect with and keep their clients satisfied.

2.3 Cloud Security Risks for E-commerce companies

Given the intense rivalry for market share between prominent businesses such as Google, Amazon, and Microsoft, as well as the development of remote work and increased online services, the cloud has emerged as one of the strongest computing platforms, offering a solid foundation for both small and large organizations. Although using cloud computing has many advantages for retailers, the problem is that security concerns like hacking and malware only get worse over time. These worries about safety can harm the image of your business with customers, result in expensive interruptions, and resulting in reduced sales.

1. Malware attack

One of the most common problems with cloud security is malicious software, called malware. Worms, viruses, adware, Trojans Trojan horses, ransomware, and spyware are employed to attack weak points in the cloud's structure. As such, the cloud computing architecture frequently includes numerous parts, such as virtual machines, or VMs, and storage containers that may be hacked by cybercriminals. Given the intense rivalry for market share between prominent businesses like Google, Amazon, and Microsoft's website, along with the rise of remote work and expanded accessibility to the internet, cloud computing has emerged as one of the most potent computing platforms, delivering a strong basis for enterprises of all sizes.

Further safety precautions can be applied by: ensuring all access to cloud systems using multiple authentication methods and a minimum level of privilege. Segment the network to ensure that, in case of a virus attack, hackers will only have a negative impact on just a tiny part of the network.

2. Data Loss

Collaboration and accessibility are cited as benefits by cloud businesses. However, there are situations when cloud configurations make it simpler for users, like retailers, to communicate data, either with internal personnel or those with outside organizations by direct invitations via email or by sharing information via public links. Despite the benefits being the cloud's major asset and the key to cooperation, the straightforward nature of transmitting information through the use of cloud computing still prepared the way for significant challenges within data loss. When data is destroyed in the cloud, it could be due to catastrophic events for which the cloud service provider is ill-prepared, malware attacks, hardware failures, distorted or lost data, and hardware errors, malfunctions in the hardware, and hardware breakdowns. Your online store must therefore regularly perform backups to deal with this issue and reduce such dangers. Your business ought to back up a number of types of data, such as personnel files, accounting data, property and tax records, digital files, and business administration materials.

2.4. Data security in cloud computing

Safety concerns are essential when using online shopping portals. Consumers need to have faith that entering their payments on your platform is secure and safe. Cloud computing offers superior security and cutting-edge solutions that helps with buffering your business's assets from malicious threats, raising client confidence and helping your brand stand out from your rivals online.

2.4.1. Various security algorithms

RSA: RSA was described by Ron Rivest, Adi Shamir and Leonard adleman in 1977. RSA algorithm is an asymmetric cryptography algorithm. Asymmetric actually means that it works on two different keys i.e Public Key and Private Key. Public key is given to everyone and the private key is private.

i. Select p, q p, q both are prime

- ii. Calculate $n = p \times q$
- iii. Calculate $\phi(n) = (p-1)(q-1)$
- iv. Selected integer e $\text{gcd}(\phi(n), e) = 1; 1 < e < \phi(n)$
- v. Calculate d $d = e^{-1} \text{ mod } \phi(n)$
- vi. Public key $KU = \{e, n\}$
- vii. Private Key $KR = \{d, n\}$

3.4.2 Data Encryption Algorithm (DEA)

Data Encryption Algorithm is now Triple Data Encryption Algorithm (3DEA) which is also known as 3DES algorithm. Data encryption Standard (DES) cipher uses 3 times to encrypt its data. A symmetric-key algorithm constructed around a Feistel network is referred to as DES. It is asymmetric key cipher, which yields an approach that is easier to use.

- i. The initial permutation function receives the 64-bit plain text.
- ii. The Initial permutation is formed on plaintext.
- iii. The initial permutation then makes two halves of the block that has been permuted.
- iv. The two halves are known as left plain text and right text.
- v. All left plaintext and right text are encrypted 16 times.
- vi. The left plaintext and right text are joined, and then the final permutation is performed on this block.
- vii. The 64-bit cipher text is now ready.

3.4.3 Blowfish Algorithm

A symmetric block called Blowfish was developed to replace the ineffective and insecure DES algorithm. Algorithm for blowfish Bruce Schneider created the blowfish rule in 1993, which could be a symmetrical key rule. It functions very similar to DES, however the key size is much smaller in DES and can be easily decoded, where as the secret size in Blowfish rule is much large and can range from 32 to 448 bits. In addition, Blowfish has sixteen round, just like DES.

- i. It has control for a lot of information.
- ii. It has an entire block size of 64 bit.
- iii. It has a key that can range in size from 32 bits to a maximum of 256 bits.
- iv. It makes use of extremely straightforward operation like expansion and XOR expansion.
- v. It makes use of an easy –to –understand outline. This promotes analysis and improves confidence in the calculation. It is rapid since a 32-bit microchip’s implementation of this method uses 26 cycle of the clock for each byte. It is reduced since it can run on a minimum of five kilobytes of memory.

3.4.2 Analysis of algorithm for E-Commerce Cloud Computing

Cloud computing centres primarily around the idea of maintaining and handling data on server virtualization so that clients and businesses everywhere in the globe are able to view the data at any time, from any location. Therefore, there ought to be a reliable safety mechanism.

RSA is secure in data transmission but data signature and its verification is strong in DES but Blowfish is more secure in cloud computing to provide data.

Table: 1 Comparison of AES and Blowfish and DES

Algorithm	DES	Blowfish	AES
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Block size	64bit	64bit	128bit
Key length	56bit	448bit	256bit
Speed	Slower	Faster	Very Faster
Security	Less Secure	More Secure	Excellent Secure

Blowfish is a solid choice, although it doesn't have a comparable block size as AES. We see AES as DES's alternative as a symmetric key encryption technique for business. It allows keys of 128,192, or 256 bits in length. The time required to check every possibility of keys at a rate of 50 billion keys per second proves the effectiveness of AES in big data security in cloud computing storage.

Conclusion

Thus, It can be seen that although the RSA method has some features, it is not an efficient way to secure E-commerce data on cloud servers. Similarly, two fish is not the ideal option for encryption because it is weaker than AES. Since passwords are primary key component in the financial sector, we are continuing in search for another reliable technology to protect data in cloud computing in future use.

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